

EUFAR FP7

DENCHAR

Development and Evaluation of Novel and Compact Hygrometers for Airborne Research

“DENCHAR-Assessment Report on the Performance of a New Suite of Hygrometers for EUFAR”

**Herman G.J. Smit (Lead),
Martina Krämer, Christian Rolf, Nicole Spelten, Andreas Petzold,
Susanne Rohs, Patrick Neis,**
(Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Jülich, Germany)

Rolf Maser
(Enviscope GmbH, Frankfurt, Germany)

Volker Ebert, Bernhard Bucholz
(Physikalisch Technische Bundesanstalt, Braunschweig, Germany)

Zoltan Bozoki & David Tatrai
(University of Szeged, Hungary)

Rod Jones, M. I. Mead
(University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)

Axel Hoff
(Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany)

Date May 2014

Contact:
Dr. Herman G.J. Smit
Research Centre Juelich (IEK-8)
52425 Juelich
E-Mail: h.smit@fz-juelich.de
Tel: +49-2461-613290

Executive Summary

Water vapour is one of the most important parameters in weather prediction and climate research. Accurate and reliable airborne measurements of water vapour are a pre-requisite to study the underlying processes in the chemistry and physics of the atmosphere. Presently, no airborne water vapour sensor exists that can measure over the entire range of water vapour content between the surface and the UT/LS region with sufficient accuracy and time resolution, not to speak of the technical requirements for quasi-routine operation.

In a joint research activity of the European Facility for Airborne Research (EUFAR) program, funded by the European Commission in FP7, we have addressed this deficit by the Development and Evaluation of Novel and Compact Hygrometer for Airborne Research (DENCHAR), including the sampling characteristics of different gas/ice inlets. The new instruments using innovative detecting technics based on tuneable diode laser technology combined with absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS) or photoacoustic spectroscopy (PAS): (i) SEALDH based on novel self-calibrating absorption spectroscopy; (ii) WASUL, based on photoacoustic spectroscopy; (iii) commercial WVSS-II, also a TDLAS hygrometer, but using 2f-detection technics.

The activity has followed an unique strategy by facilitating new instrumental developments together with conducting extensive testing, both in the laboratory and during in-flight operation. Hereby, in order to obtain unbiased results of the instrument intercomparisons, all laboratory and in-flight-performance tests during the project were conducted as blind intercomparisons and were first analyzed and evaluated after each PI had submitted the data to the DENCHAR-coordinator. Further, during in-flight testing onboard the Learjet research aircraft the DENCHAR hygrometers were compared to the FISH instrument. The FISH itself was calibrated to the reference frost point hygrometer MBW DP30 in the laboratory. The FISH instrument has participated in several international aircraft and laboratory hygrometer intercomparisons as one of the so-called 'core' instruments'. In other terms: FISH can be assumed as the transfer standard between aircraft measurements and the ground based MBW DP30 reference frostpoint hygrometer.

After successful testing, the new instruments were integrated in an autonomous small flight package (SFP) that could in principle be operated at any research aircraft in EUFAR. The SFP with the new DENCHAR instruments have been intensively tested and compared to the FISH and among each other. The results has been evaluated and compiled in an assessment report with following major outcome:

- All four DENCHAR-instruments show very consistent behavior in their respective measuring ranges. They deviate by less than about 5-10%, in-flight against FISH as well as among each other. They also show similar consistent results in the laboratory against DP30 (MBW-Frost point hygrometer). Thus, all results can be traced to the DP30 reference instrument within about 10% or even better.
- Performance of the new DENCHAR instruments is generally good from VMR = 20,000 ppmv down to 20-100 ppmv, achieving agreement within 10% uncertainty or better.
- Instruments like SEALDH or WaSul, both using laser absorption spectroscopy detection methods, are able to achieve sampling rates of 10-100 Hz. This means they may be applied for fast measurements of gaseous water vapour > 10 ppmv, which open research areas on water vapour flux measurements or eddy correlation studies
- WaSuL has the potential to measure gaseous + total H₂O simultaneously for VMR > 10 ppmv: one prototype will fly in the near future aboard one Canadian research A/C, and further developments will be continued in the European IGAS-project. It has to be noted

that an older version of WaSul is part of the suite of water vapor instruments aboard the CARIBIC-aircraft.

- The measuring capabilities of the DENCHAR instruments SEALDH, WaSul and WVSS-II are remarkable good and are comparable with the results of intercomparisons of well established airborne hygrometer done for example at Aquavit (Fahey et al., 2009)
- The commercial WVSS-II system can be used for VMR > 200 ppmv in unattended mode and can do reliable water vapour measurements within $\pm(5-10)\%$ uncertainty. However, at lower humidities the instrument gets not reliable anymore because it can alter its performance: Sometimes the WVSS-II can even measure very well down to 20-40 ppmv, but at other times the same instrument reaches its detection limit already at 200 ppmv water vapour mixing ratios.

Parallel, DENCHAR has also addressed the performance of different inlet systems. The following inlets were compared to each other: (i) forward facing inlet; (ii) backward facing inlet; (iii) Rosemount (TAT housing) inlet; (iv) wall plate inlet. From all in-flight testings no measurement artifacts caused by specific characteristics of an inlet could be identified. For the Rosemount inlets it was often discussed if evaporated ice residuals might influence the H₂O signal. Up to now it was unknown if wall plate inlets properly sample the gas phase. From this study we can conclude that the latter two inlet types are also suitable for representative measurements of H₂O. Our conclusions, however, are only valid in the temperature and pressure range studied here, that is $T < 240$ K (cirrus cloud range) and $p < 500$ hPa (altitudes > 5km). For warmer conditions at lower altitudes (mixed phase and warm cloud range) with much higher H₂O concentrations, the possibility of condensation of water in the inlet lines or, inside of clouds, splashing of droplets at the inlet tip is much larger. These effects can cause inlet induced measurement artifacts. It is a future task to study inlet characteristics under conditions typical for the lower troposphere.

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1. Introduction

Water vapour is the most prominent parameter in weather prediction and climate research. The understanding of its distribution in the upper troposphere (UT) and lower stratosphere (LS), which is the most sensitive region with respect to changes in radiative forcing, is crucial for the further development of global climate models. Accurate and reliable measurements of water vapour are a pre-requisite to study the underlying processes in the chemistry and physics of the atmosphere. Presently, no airborne humidity sensor exists that covers the entire range of water vapour content between the surface and the UT/LS region with sufficient accuracy and time resolution, not to speak of the technical requirements for quasi-routine operation.

DENCHAR (Development and Evaluation of Novel and Compact Hygrometer for Airborne Research), a joint research activity of EUFAR, have addressed this deficit by developing and characterizing novel or improved compact hygrometers, including the sampling characteristics of different gas/ice inlets. The activity have followed an unique strategy by facilitating new instrumental developments together with conducting extensive testing, both in the laboratory and in-flight operation.

In the five years period that the DENCHAR-project has been conducted new instruments have been developed and/or extensively tested in the laboratory as well as in-flight onboard of research aircraft: (i) SEALDH based on novel self-calibrating TDLAS hygrometer; (ii) WASUL-photo acoustic hygrometer using tunable diode laser too; (iii) commercial WVSS-II, also a TDLAS hygrometer, but using 2f-detection techniques (iv) SAW-frost point hygrometer using surface acoustic wave detection technics. Parallel a new airborne ultra fast thermometer (UFT2) to do fast temperature measurements at KHz-sampling rate has been developed and intensively tested in the laboratory (wind duct measurements) or in-flight.

In the course of the project the DENCHAR instruments have been extensively tested through comparison with advance instruments in the laboratory (Ly(α) resonance fluorescence or DP30 frost point hygrometer) or in-flight (FISH) aboard a Learjet research aircraft during several campaigns between 2010 and 2013. All laboratory & in-flight-performance tests were done as blind intercomparisons this mean that each instrument PI has to submit his data and first after all data were submitted at the referee, i.e. coordinator of DENCHAR, all campaign data were made available to each DENCHAR-instrument PI for further analysis of the data.

In this assessment report we have evaluated the DENCHAR results obtained from the different intercomparison campaigns, whereby the focus will be on the results obtained during the last campaigns. In chapter 2 each instrument will be briefly presented in term of state of the art, major developments, performance and stability based on the work done in the laboratory. Chapter 3 will present and evaluate the different inlet system, which were used during the three research aircraft campaigns. In Chapter 4 the major performance facts of the different DENCHAR instruments are briefly summarized, which is based on the results obtained from investigations done in the laboratory in the course of DENCHAR-project. Independently in Summer 2013 laboratory comparisons with an accurate DP30-frost point hygrometer have been made, which are reported in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 is given the evaluation of the performance of the DENCHAR instruments during the in-flight comparisons made with the FISH-hygrometer, but also among the DENCHAR hygrometer themselves. Chapter 7 gives a concluding overview with outlook, while here also recommendations for EUFAR are given, which are based on the experiences made during DENCHAR.

2. DENCHAR Instruments: State of the Art, Major Developments, Performance & Stability

Between the end of 2008 and spring 2012 the four new types of hygrometer using different detection techniques as well as the novel ultra fast thermometer have been developed. Parallel laboratory tests of the individual prototype instruments were made at the humidity calibration facilities at FZJ in Jülich, Germany. In addition, in May 2011 the instruments were tested on their in-flight performances during a research aircraft intercomparison campaign (IFCC-2011). Between March 2012 and the end of 2012 the instruments were integrated in a small flight package (SFP) (See Figure 2-1) that can be flown autonomously on any research aircraft. The SFP was initially designed and constructed for endurance testing of the DENCHAR-instruments. This means that the SFP had to be flown without any operator on board during routine flight operation of the Learjet 35A D-CGFD. Because we did not get flight allowance to fly the SFP unattended aboard the Learjet aircraft we had to change our evaluation programme from endurance testing into calibration and in-flight comparison, which we finally did during the AIRTOSS (AIRcraft Towed Sensor Shuttle) experiments. Aboard the Learjet 35A D-CGFD the SFP was thereby operated side by side with the Lyman (α) FISH hygrometer together with a suite of cloud detecting instruments.

In this chapter each instrument is briefly presented in term of state of the art, major developments, performance and stability based on the work done in the laboratory. Although the FISH instrument is not a DENCHAR instrument we incorporate it here in this chapter because during DENCHAR the FISH has been our “transfer standard” instrument . The FISH is always calibrated with the DP30 frost point hygrometer, which calibration is traceable to a primary water vapor standard.

Figure 2-1 DENCHAR Rack SFP: Rack mounted in Learjet A/C (left) and Design of SFP (right)

2.1 DENCHAR Reference Instrument: FISH

(Christian Rolf, Martina Krämer, Nicole Spelten)

2.1.1 Instrument description

The airborne Lyman- α photofragment fluorescence hygrometer FISH (Fast In-situ Stratospheric Hygrometer) is a well established instrument for measuring water vapour in the range of 1 to 1000 ppmv. The FISH (See Figure 2.1-1) is especially built for measuring low water vapour concentration prevailing in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (Zoeger *et al.* 1999, Schiller *et al.* 2008). The aircraft instrument was designed and built in 1998 and up to now the FISH instrument has been integrated and flown on many research aircraft (e.g. Geophysica M55, NASA WB-57, Learjet 36A, DLR Falcon 20-E5) on 39 scientific campaigns with around 1800 flight hours. Beside these many campaigns with a focus on atmospheric science, the FISH is often compared to other instruments during several laboratory and in-flight intercomparison campaigns (AquaVit-1 2007, AquaVit-2 2013, and MACPEX 2011).

The measurement principle is based on photofragment fluorescence. The Lyman- α radiation emitted by a flow charge lamp split the water vapour into an excited OH* and H molecules. The amount of fluorescence photons emitted by the relaxation of OH* is directly proportional to the mixing ratio of water vapour. By measuring this photons with a photomultiplier tube (PMT) and the intensity of the light source (I_0) the concentration of water vapour can be determined. In figure 2 the FISH measurement principle is shown. Directly before the flow lamp a rotating mirror is placed. With the help of this rotating mirror the fluorescence photons (N_g) can be measured in position 1 with the PMT, where all the Lyman- α is transmitted into the measurement cell. In mirror position 2 the light of the lamp is reflected into an ionization cell to estimate I_0 . The background of the lamp is measured in position 3, where all the Lyman- α radiation is blocked and only the background fluorescence photons (N_u) are measured with the PMT. This leads to the FISH formula to determine the water vapour mixing ratio μ with the help of two calibration factors c_k and f_u :

$$\mu = c_k \cdot \frac{N_g - f_u \cdot N_u}{I_0}$$

The FISH has to be regularly calibrated against a reference instrument at different water vapor concentrations and different cell pressures to determine the calibrations factors c_k and f_u . This reference is currently a MBW DP30 frost point mirror which allows to measure the water vapor concentration very accurate. For calibration we use a calibration bench consisting of a humidifier and a mixing unit operated with synthetic dry air.

Figure 2.1-1: Principle of the FISH instrument

2.1.2 Performance and Stability

The Fast In-situ Stratospheric Hygrometer (FISH) is a well-established instrument, which provides high quality measurements of water vapour. To ensure the data quality the instrument is regularly calibrated and validated as described below.

Calibration

The frequent calibration of the FISH instrument is important to ensure the quality of the water vapour measurements. The FISH calibration bench including the reference instrument MBW DP30 is shown in Figure 2.1-2. The calibration procedure is done at 6 to 8 humidity levels ranging from 3 ppmv to 600 ppmv to cover nearly the full measurement range. The pressure within the measuring cell can be adjusted independently from 80 to 500 hPa. So each humidity level contains normally three pressure levels (e.g. 100 hPa, 250 hPa, 400 hPa) with temporal length of 10 minutes. Including the pre-flushing of the whole system before the calibration procedure one calibration needs around 6-8 hours of time.

Figure 2.1-2: FISH calibration bench

The instrument is calibrated before and after each flight. This allows to account for any changes during flight operation of the instrument. Additionally, these frequent calibrations indicate if the FISH and the calibration procedure are stable during the whole campaign. During AIRTOSS II the FISH was calibrated three times. The resulting calibration factors were very stable and the changes were less than 0.5 %.

The accuracy of the FISH measurement is mainly determined by the accuracy of the reference instrument. The MBW DP30 has an accuracy of 4 %, which is confirmed during several intercomparisons with the PTB permeation source, other MBW DP30 and MBW 373 as well as Thunder humidity generator. The reproducibility of the calibration and resulting calibration factors enlarge the accuracy of the FISH instrument to $\pm 7 \% + 0.3 \text{ ppmv}$ for mixing ratios of 4 to 1000 ppmv.

Intercomparison

The FISH instrument is compared intensively to other water vapour instruments during the two AquaVit campaigns 2007 (*Fahey et al. 2009*), and 2013 at the AIDA cloud chamber in Karlsruhe, Germany. Additionally, in-flight intercomparisons are performed during the MACPEX campaign that took place 2011 in Houston, Texas (*Rollins et al. 2013*). Intercomparisons of different instruments showed larger deviations in the low water vapour range (< 10 ppmv), while at levels larger than 10 ppmv the measurements are within the uncertainties of the instruments. As an example, Figure 2.1-3 shows an intercomparison of FISH with the Lyman- α hygrometer HWV (Harvard Water Vapor), the open-path TDL DLH, and closed-path TDL Alias during the airborne field campaign MACPEX. The agreement of all four instruments is very good in general. The data-points are very close to the one to one line and the deviations are mostly less than 10 % (dashed lines).

Figure 2.1-3: Flight on 26.04.11: FISH MACPEX intercomparison of water vapor data outside of clouds with the Lyman- α HWV (Harvard Water Vapor), open-path TDL DLH, and the closed-path TDL Alias.

2.2 DENCHAR Instrument: SEALDH

(Bernhard Bucholz and Volker Ebert)

2.2.1 State of the Art

The SEALDH-I and SEALDH-II instruments (See Figure 2.2-1), *SEALDH* = acronym for “selective extractive airborne diode laser hygrometer”, are both largely developed in the frame of the EUFAR DENCHAR project. The basic spectrometric method behind the instrument is calibration-free, direct tuneable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (dTDLAS) which has been developed for several years in our working group as one of our research priorities (*Ebert and Wolfrum, 2000, Ebert 2004, 2006, Witzel et al., 2013*). The high state of development and quality of this approach has been demonstrated in several applications and

instrument comparisons (*Fahey et al., 2009*) with large, laboratory-typical setups. Newly developed in recent years was a dedicated, compact, highly integrated fairly autonomous airborne package of the 1379 nm TDLAS hygrometer. Many problems had to be solved to minimize volume and power consumption without compromising the instrument performance. Numerous technological advancements were needed to achieve this: Special, versatile, low-noise spectrometer electronics, new highly compact, miniaturized, low-volume, multi-path absorption cells, a fully automated control and pre-evaluation software and many other sub-components had to be developed – often for the first time.

In particular the excellent linearity and high dynamic range of dTDLAS is in many applications an important advantage as this also allows to relatively simply expand the measurement range e.g. by enlarging the optical path length. However in the class of optical instruments as compact as SEALDH length extension is not that easy to use due to size restrictions. On the other hand especially for water vapour a wide range between 10 and 30000 ppmv had to be realized to cover the entire humidity range up to the lower stratosphere, so that a typical multi cell approach falls short due to the strong limitations in size.

Figure 2.2-1: SEALDH-I (bottom) and the advanced version SEALDH-II (top). Both instruments are fit for action

2.2.2 Major Developments

Both SEALDH instruments are completely self-developed and set up from general commercial part like lasers, detectors etc. This rather time-consuming approach leads to the benefit of a perfect fit between an instrument and its externally dictated measurement conditions. Combined with the physical understanding, which is based on full sets of housekeeping data, it is possible to establish a higher trust level of data assurance as it is possible with (protected) commercial instruments, which quite often have to be treated as black boxes. So several working steps such as selection of the ideal absorption line, characterizing the laser, developing extractive measurement cells, set up the instrument with all the mechanical workload, wiring etc., writing the control software for a fully controlled and

autonomous operation has to be done to get finally these instruments for validation and intercomparison (Bucholz *et al.*, 2012).

The first laboratory intercomparison was done in 2010 with an preliminary study, called of SEALDH-0, to test and validate some of the key parts for the later use, which has already been published (Bucholz *et al.*, 2013). In May 2011 SEALDH-I was the first cal-free dTDLAS instrument which has ever been used in an airborne application (Bucholz and Ebert, 2013). Compared with the well-established Lyman-alpha instrument FISH from the Research Centre Jülich (Zöger *et al.*, 1999) in the lower (<600 ppmv) H₂O concentration range and the commercial WVSS-II instruments (>200 ppmv), which are also part of the DENCHAR project, the calibration free SEALDH-I showed very nice results. However, in the low mixing ratio area, the calculated offset uncertainty of 25 ppmv and several desirable additions of housekeeping data lead to the SEALDH-II (Figure 2.2-2) development, which solved these problems (calculated offset uncertainty 3 ppmv) and improved the data trust level with more than 80 different and independent housekeeping data and derivatives. Both instruments save the full spectroscopic signals, so called raw data, to allow a detailed subsequent post flight-evaluation. Both instruments have a linear uncertainty of 4.3%.

Figure 2.2-2: The SEALDH-II instrument

2.2.3 Performance and Stability

The calibration-free approach of dTDLAS doesn't rely on a calibration procedure, i.e. on a comparison of the TDLAS instrument with a reference water vapour source or water vapour analyser. Instead TDLAS is operated in a first principle mode and only needs a certain set of measurement parameters and a spectroscopic model to derive via a fitting process the water vapour mixture fraction. Not to calibrate does not mean that the instrument must not be validated. To demonstrate its performance level, the SEALDH instruments were validated at the highest possible level via a direct side by side comparison with the primary humidity standard at the National Metrology Institute of Germany (Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt). These comparisons showed that the SEALDH-II instrument possesses a long-term reproducibility of < 0.5% in the worst case and 0.17% in average in the full pressure range (60hPa-1000hPa). This performance comes close to the uncertainty range of the primary standards itself. The measured deviations of SEALDH to the primary standard were smaller than the calculated uncertainty at each validated point between 10 and 25000 ppmv, with a small but well understood pressure dependency.

Furthermore SEADLH-II also participated in the AquaVit-II intercomparison in Karlsruhe, which was the follow-up campaign of AquaVit-I (Fahey *et al.*, 2009), which gathered many worldwide airborne research instruments based on a multitude of different technics. The data were recently evaluated and submitted but the comparison evaluation is on-going at the moment.

2.3 DENCHAR Instrument: WaSul

(David Tatrai and Zoltan Bozoki)

2.3.1 State of the Art

The complete WaSul-Hygro rack (Figure 2.3-1) consists of a controlling electronics, one room temperature DFB (Distributed FeedBack) diode laser, two measuring cells, two pressure sensors (Psen) and two mass flow controllers (MFC) (Figure 2.3-2).

Figure 2.3-1: Photo of WaSul-Hygro taken during flight test preparation

Figure 2.3-2: The schematic layout of WaSul-Hygro

WaSul-Hygro is a photoacoustic (PA) spectroscopy based dual channel hygrometer. The PA effect is the conversion of electromagnetic radiation into acoustic waves through consecutive

processes of absorption, non-radiative relaxation, heat diffusion and thermal expansion. The dual channel layout uniquely gives the possibility for simultaneous water vapour and total water content measurements although during the EUFAR project the two channels of the instrument were combined to sample air from the same source. A telecommunication type DFB diode laser is used to measure the volume mixing ratio (VMR) of water vapour at its absorption line at the wavelength of 1.393 μm . The system at its current stage requires a very detailed calibration at different pressures for each individual instrument (*D. Tátrai, in preparation*), which is done at the University of Szeged.

Unlike its predecessor, which is in operation since 2004 in the CARIBIC project (*C. A. M. Brenninkmeijer, 2007*) and which requires a continuous in-flight calibration against a slow response chilled mirror hygrometer (Buck CR2) the present version is capable for standalone operation. A very similar version of the present system is (manufactured by Hilase Ltd) has been used since June, 2013 by the Environment Canada for airborne cloud measurements. This system was designed for operation in the 0.5-60,000 ppmv volume VMR and 100-1100 mbar pressure ranges. Tests of the system during the AquaVIT campaign (*Web link*) shown the lowest detectable VMR was about 0.3 ppm.

2.3.2. Major Developments

The predecessor of WaSul Hygro has been operated in the CARIBIC project since 2004. The earlier experiments have shown that the dynamic range, sensitivity, lower detection limit and the altogether performance of the system are appropriate for airborne applications up to the lower stratospheric regions. But that system required regular maintenance, and continuous in-flight calibration as the long term stability was not adequate. Furthermore the VMR calculation was only possible by continuous comparison with a reference instrument.

During DENCHAR several hardware and software developments have been achieved in order to improve the performance of the system and turn it into an accurate, precise, standalone and reliable tool for environment research. The most important ones are the followings:

- Laser wavelength change: The first version of the system was made at 1371 nm, where significant relaxation with oxygen decreased the sensitivity especially at low humidities. The new selected wavelength is 1393 nm where the cross effect with oxygen is definitely much lower while no other disturbing effects were observed.
- Sensitivity change: In order to cover humidities in the 0.5-30000 ppm range one sensitivity change has to be implemented to extend the dynamic range by an order of magnitude. Previously this was done by modifying the modulation frequency of the laser but now the gain of the signal conditioning circuit can be automatically adjusted. This led to more stable and more linear operation.
- Laser wavelength stabilization: The key question of the performance of the system is the stability and accuracy of the wavelength of the applied laser. The wavelength of the laser can be adjusted by its temperature and driving current. The stability of the temperature decides the stability of the wavelength. With the optimization of the stabilization parameters and method the stability of the wavelength could have been improved by a factor of five. The accuracy of the wavelength is limited by the accuracy of the driving current. For its accurate setting through the feedback of a fast PA spectrum measurement a patented method has been developed (*Z. Bozóki, 2013; D. Tátrai, 2013*).

The above listed developments ensured the stable and reliable operation of Wasul-Hygro. However, the other key question in the operation is the accurate VMR calculation from the measured values. The first trials (*M. Szakáll, 2006*) turned to be confused by significant

uncertainties. Therefore a new method had to be developed. During DENCHAR several methods were tried, the latest and up to now the best method is the following: Calibration curves are recorded at different pressures. These curves form a surface in the pressure, PA signal and VMR space. For VMR calculation a two-step method has been developed: First from the measured PA signals VMR values are calculated at all the pressures used during the calibration and then from the resulted dataset the actual WVC is determined by interpolation to the actual pressure using a cubic spline algorithm. The precision of this method is the same as the instruments one and the accuracy is limited by the calibration reference. The evaluation time of this method is in the orders of a millisecond on a general purpose PC or notebook giving the possibility for real-time VMR calculation.

2.3.3 Performance and Stability

WaSul-Hygro has to be calibrated at several constant pressures during the system preparation. For this purpose a simple but reliable tool was made (*D. Tátrai, in preparation*). Its core humidity generator (HG) is homemade, based on temperature dependent saturation. This HG was calibrated against a chilled mirror hygrometer at the Hungarian National Office of Measures in the 1-25000 ppmV range. In VMR better than 0.5% + 0.3 ppmV repeatability was observed at any measured temperature, while in frost point a constant 1.2 K offset was determined which is corrected before VMR calculation. As the VMR calculation method can reproduce any VMR value of the HG within its precision range at any possible pressures now the accuracy of the system is limited by the HG-s one.

Through the developments WaSul-Hygro was several times blind tested at the Environment Simulation Facility (*Smit, 2000*) (Jülich) and by the end of the developments better than 4% of accuracy was achieved over the whole covered VMR and pressure ranges. Figure 2.3-3. Of course the system can also be validated by other reference humidity generators.

Figure 2.3-3: Comparison cross plot between WaSul-Hygro and the ESF chamber reference instruments.

Experiments with similar PA systems developed by the research group that developed WaSul-Hygro too shows that the calibration constants of such a system don't vary significantly within 5 years so the recalibration intervals of WaSul-Hygro can be such long periods.

2.4 DENCHAR Instrument: WVSS-II

(Herman G.J. Smit)

2.4.1 State of the Art

The complete WVSS-II system (see Figure 2.4-1) consists of: (i) the System Electronics Box (SEB) containing the TDLAS-water vapour detector (including process controlling electronics); (ii) Air Sampler (AS) to be mounted on the aircraft skin, and heated inlet and outlet hoses for connecting SEB to the AS.

Figure 2.4-1: The components of the aircraft humidity sensor type WVSS-II+X (SpectraSensors Inc., USA).

The WVSS (Water Vapor Sampling System) is based on tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS) using Beer's absorption law. A small, near infrared diode laser is used to measure the atmospheric mixing ratio of water vapour at its absorption line at the wavelength of 1.37 μm . The sensor uses 2nd order harmonic (2f) detection techniques, which requires a calibration at different pressures and temperatures for each individual instrument (May *et al.* 1999), which is done by the manufacturer.

Since 2006 the WVSS-II has been integrated and flown on 25 aircraft of the UPS-carrier fleet during normal flight operation within the USA under the responsibility of the American National Weather Service. Meanwhile more than 150 WVSS-II instruments are flown on American in-service aircraft. Although the WVSS-II has been installed on a large number of aircraft, documentation and specifications of WVSS-II performance is still very poor. No peer refereed publications exist. Only a spare number of validations for P and T conditions up to Z=6 km exist as internal reports, but above in the middle/upper troposphere and lower stratosphere at low (specific) humidities, low temperatures and low pressures no validation of WVSS-II exists. This means many important questions about performance of WVSS-II in general and particularly in middle/upper troposphere and lower stratosphere have to be answered. One of them involves also maintenance of long-term stability after an initial calibration in the laboratory

2.4.2. Some Instrumental Aspects

The first prototype WVSS-II instrument we tested in 2005/2006 at our Environmental Simulation Facility against accurate humidity instruments. These earlier experiments have shown that the WVSS-II sensor might be sufficient for humidity measurements in the lower and middle troposphere but not suitable for upper tropospheric or lower stratospheric measurements. Since then the manufacturer Spectra Sensors Inc. did several instrumental modifications on hardware as well as on the software for data processing. An upgraded version WVSS-II had become available in March 2010.

In the commercial version a so called wall plate air sampler is used. The air sampler (Figure 2.4-2) is mounted with its length axis parallel to the outward flow that forces a sampled air flow through the SEB. In order to avoid any condensation the inlet hose as well as the sampling tube (=detection cell) are electrically heated. The targeted temperature inside of the sampling tube is about 35 °C. This once has been chosen to be always beyond the maximum dew point the atmosphere ever can reach.

Figure 2.4-2: The functionality of the WVSS-II components.

A critical aspect is the design of the inlet system. Crucial question thereby is in how far this type of inlet system is suitable for humidity measurements in the MT- and UT/LS-region. In DENCHAR we have tested the wall plate sensor in-flight and occasionally it showed that it might sample also wet boundary layer air, which contaminated the WVSS-II-measurements significantly. During the DENCHAR project we had two different WVSS-II instruments available to investigate and compare their performances. Two times we had the opportunity to fly one WVSS-II system with the wall plate sampler and simultaneously the other instrument at the common inlet system of the SEALDH and WaSul instrument to investigate performance of the wall plate.

For this wall plate inlet system numerical fluid dynamic simulation experiment were done. The numerical calculations showed that definitely the sampled air has been in contact with the aircraft fuselage and therefore has a high risk of contamination with water on its surface. Therefore, large gradients e.g. flying in cloud or from the moist lower troposphere to higher altitudes are unlikely to be measured with such an inlet. This has also been seen in-flight, although we could not fully distinguish between the performance of the WVSS-II detector or the wall plate sampler.

2.4.3 Performance and Stability

The WVSS-II is based on TDLAS using 2f-detection techniques which means that it has to be calibrated regularly against an accurate (e.g. frostpoint hygrometer) at different pressure steps

of 100 hPa between 200 and 1000 hPa and different VMR levels between 0 and 20,000 ppmv. The calibration is done by the manufacturer. Within DENCHAR we have several times compared the two instruments in the laboratory the two different instruments against accurate reference instruments (DP30-frost point hygrometer or Lyman (a) Fluorescence Hygrometer).

Figure 2.4-3: Example of a validation of WVSS-II (S/N0370) against DP30 made at 15.August 2013 before the second AIRTOSS campaign in September 2013

An example of a comparison of WVSS-II against DP30 is shown in Figure 2.4-3. Based on the regular comparison of the instrument it showed a precision of about 3% with an instrumental uncertainty of 5-10% over humidity range of 15,000 ppmv down to 20 ppmv. However, in other campaigns and also in the laboratory we observed cases that below 100 ppmv the instrument is not always stable. Up to now we could not identify why this occurs.ü

2.5 DENCHAR Instrument: SAW

(M.I. Mead and Rod Jones)

2.5.1 State of the Art

The CAMP SAW hygrometer (SAW-I) was used at the start of the EUFAR/DENCHAR program (2008) and was tested in the Forschungszentrum Jülich Environmental Simulation Facility (ESF) to be initially evaluated against the chamber reference instruments (Lyman Alpha and General Eastern chilled mirror hygrometers). From these initial tests it was decided that the SAW-I instrument was suitable for operation in the mid troposphere. It was also decided that the SAW-I was suitable for update as part of EUFAR/DENCHAR program to extend its operational window into the upper troposphere.

The redesign of the SAW hygrometer was based on updates of the electronics (PCB redesign and control algorithm rewrite) as well as the physical housing of the hygrometer. SAW-II was developed for use in the EUFAR/DENCHAR project. This instrument was significantly reduced in size and weight relative to SAW-I. The thermal response of the instrument is key to its operation both at speed and at low water vapour mixing ratios and temperatures.

2.5.2. Major Developments

SAW-II was tested on a number of occasions in the ESF, beginning in 2010. A number of smaller tests in the ESF followed this initial set of tests all focused on the same operational

parameter testing of the dew/frostpoint signal locking system. These tests were focused on operational feedback control and resulted in updated feedback control controls for use with the revised driver and control electronics. These tests resulted in significant dew/frostpoint signal locking system improvements.

During the DENCHAR-Laboratory Inter-Comparison Campaign in Fall 2010 the improved control mechanism for the SAW-II were tested extensively thereby avoiding instrument signal oscillation and over damping of the dew/frost point signal. The primary outcome was the implementation of a series of feedback control parameters dependent on atmospheric temperature and pressure. Further ESF tests in 2011 were to test the enclosure designed for use in the DENCHAR-IFCC flight campaigns. Sample flow and thermal control were investigated in detail and the assembly optimised for the flight campaign in May/June 2013 (See Figure 2.5-1).

Figure 2.5-1: CAD diagrams of the SAW instrument enclosure (cut away and external view). Right hand figure shows the SAW-II instrument mounted on the window plate aboard the DENCHAR-IFCC Learjet.

Figure 2.5-2: SAW flight 4 data (log scale to highlight differences) showing areas of excellent agreement with the campaign reference instrument s as well as a period where the SAW could not remove heat sufficiently.

The response time of the instrument is $>1\text{Hz}$ (at 8 readings per second multiplexed). From the ESF tests the instrument operational range is 0-215 K. Additional thermal isolation would potentially extend operation into the upper. Between 215 K and 275 K the instrument operates with an accuracy of $\pm 1-4\%$. Below 215 K the accuracy is approximately $\pm 1-5\%$. The observed main issue with this installation is heat loss. The maximum ΔT is variable, depending on the operational environment. During the airborne campaign this ranged between 55/60 – 35°C (see figure 2.5-2).

The instrument was installed and flown in all flights as part of the DENCHAR-IFCC campaign (May/June 2011). SAW-II did not fly flown during the AIRTOSS I & II campaigns (2013). Insufficient space was available on the Learjet mounting plate for these campaigns.

3. Inlet Systems

(Martina Krämer, Christian Rolf)

In the frame of the DENCHAR project, four different types of inlets are used: one standard forward inlet (see Figure 3-1, right panel; Krämer and Afchine, 2004; Krämer et al., 2013) and a backward facing inlet (see Figure 1, left panel; Bange et al., 2013), both provided by enviscope. The other two are a wall plate (Afchine et al., 2011) and a Rosemount inlet (McQuaid et al., 2013).

Figure 3-1: Inlets systems used during the Learjet aircraft campaigns IFCC (May 2011) and AIRTOSS (May & September 2013), both equipped with the DENCHAR water vapour sensors SEALDH, WASUL, WVSS-II #1 as well as a WVSS-II #2 and the FISH instrument.

The inlets are deployed in two configurations on the enviscope Learjet during the airborne field campaigns IFCC (May 2011) and AIRTOSS (May & September 2013). In 2011, the DENCHAR water vapour sensors SEALDH, WASUL, WVSS-II #1 used the backward inlet, which is faced backward to avoid the sampling of ice crystals and heated to avoid memory effects. WVSS-II #2 is connected to the forward facing wall plate inlet (heated inlet hose), designed to sample only gas phase water vapour. A CR-2 -which was plugged to the backward inlet- was also operated at the Learjet. In 2013 the DENCHAR instruments used the Rosemount TAT housing, also designed to sample only gas phase water vapour. The WVSS-II #2 again uses the forward facing wall plate inlet. During both campaigns the FISH instrument was attached to the standard forward facing enviscope inlet. With this inlet type ice crystals are sampled in addition to the gas phase water vapour (=total water). It is heated to evaporate the ice crystals and to avoid memory effects.

Figure 3-2 shows time series of two flights during IFCC 2011, one on 31 May (upper panel) and the other on 1 June (lower panel). In the water vapour range > 100 ppmv, on 31 May the

highest H₂O concentrations were detected by FISH (fwd) and WVSS #1 (wall-plate), while WVSS #2 and CR-2 (both bwd) measured slightly lower values. On 1 June, WVSS #1 (wall-plate) measured the highest and WVSS #2 & CR-2 (both bwd) the lowest H₂O gas phase concentrations, while FISH (fwd) is in between.

Figure 3-2: Time series of WVSS#1 (wall plate inlet), WVSS#2 and CR2 (backward inlet) as well as FISH (standard forward inlet) during the flights 31 May (left panel) and 01 June 2011 (right panel), IFCC-2011.

Figure 3-3: Time series of WVSS#2 (wall plate inlet), WVSS#1 + WASUL + SEALDH (Rosemount inlet) as well as FISH (standard forward inlet) during the flight at 4. September, AIRTOSS 2013.

Note that the peaks in the FISH measurements between 11 and 12 o'clock are caused by ice crystals entering the fwd inlet. In the water vapour range < 100 ppmv, much larger differences between the instruments can be seen. This is interpreted as an effect of the different measuring ranges of the instruments (see Section 6-5, Figure 6-7): the WVSS instruments are not designed to measure H_2O below about 100ppmv. The CR-2 is able to detect H_2O down to about 2 ppmv, but at a low time resolution. In many -but not all- cases the CR-2 is not able to follow the fast changes during aircraft operation. Altogether, the differences in the measurements are small and not traceable to a specific inlet type. The same conclusion holds for the AIRTOSS campaign in 2013, which can be seen in Figure 3-3.

A more general comparison of H_2O measurements is shown in Figure 6-7, where scatter plots for all AIRTOSS flights are produced for various instruments (the inlet types are noted in the panels). The agreement between the instruments is discussed in Section 6-5 and 6-6. Here, it should be noted that no obvious deviation from the 1:1 line of the scatter plots can be attributed to a specific inlet.

4. Performance Facts

At the end of the DENCHAR project it is here the purpose to summarize the instrumental developments achieved in quantifiable terms. For each DENCHAR-instrument a factsheet have been prepared (See Annex-1) given an overview of the major instrumental specifications. Thereby, it had been attempted to keep it for each instrument as general as possible, this also for reasons of comparability. The factsheets have been compiled into Table 4-1 given the key instrumental specifications such as:

1. Pressure range
2. Detected quantity
3. Time response
4. Precision
5. Overall uncertainty
6. Detection range

For the sake of completeness and comparability, although FISH is not a DENCHAR instrument, we added it to the factsheets and in Table-4-1 because in the entire DENCHAR project the FISH instrument participated as our transfer standard to the DP30-frostpoint hygrometer as our primary reference instrument.

Table 4-1: Performance Facts for DENCHAR-Instruments and FISH

Instrument	Pressure Range (hPa) [1]	Detected Quantity [2]	Time Response (sec.) [3]	Precision [4]	Uncertainty [5]	Detection Range (ppmv) [6]
FISH	50-500	VMR (ppmv)	1	1 % or 0.3 ppmv below 4 ppmv	7% + 0.3ppmv	1-1000 ppmv
SEALDH-II	1-1050 hPa	Molar density	0.5	0.083 ppmv at 1 sec	4.3% +/- 3 ppmv ^[6]	0.5-50,000
WaSuL	50-1050	Molar density	< 3	better than 0.3 ppm + 0.5% of reading	better than 5%	0.5 - 60000 ppmV
WVSS-II	200-1050	Molar density	2s	1% or 2 ppmv	±5% or ±50 ppmv	5-60,000 ppmv
SAW	100-1050	Temperature	1	3%	±5%	20-10000

Comments on Table 4-1 for FISH

[1] The increasing optical thickness within the measurement cell determines an upper limit of 500 hPa or even 1000 ppmv.

[2] N/A

[3] The time response of 1 second is due to flow limitations and integration time for low humidities (< 10 ppmv).

[4] Determined from 1 Hz data using the variance (squared standard deviation) of the measurements under different stable H₂O conditions.

[5] The uncertainty includes the accuracy, the precision, and the detection limit. The accuracy is mainly determined by the accuracy of the reference instrument MBW DP30 (4 %) and the deviation of calibrations factors during one campaign.

[6] Calculated uncertainty, not measured!

Comments on Table 4-1 for SEALDH-II

- [1] Upper limit defined by internal pressure sensor
- [2] No calibration due to first principles concept
- [3] Flow limited (bulk flow estimation), 7std l/min at 200 hPa; optical time resolution: 140 Hz;
- [4] Determined via ALLAN variance
- [5] Absolute reproducibility of measurements, validated at National Primary Standard, calibration-free results.
- [6] Calculated uncertainty, not measured!

Comments on Table 4-1 for WaSul

- [1] The lower limit for effective photo acoustic (PA) signal generation is about 20 mbar but for precise measurements a bit higher pressures are necessary. The 50 mbar is a reasonable lower limit for the measurements. The 1050 mbar as upper limit is not a limitation of the instrument but of the atmosphere.
- [2] N/A
- [3] Flow limited (bulk flow estimation), 7std l/min at 200 hPa; optical time resolution: 140 Hz;
- [4] The presented values are influenced by the noise of the applied humidity generator. Measurements performed with a generally the same instrument during a non-DENCHAR measurement campaign (AquaVIT2-b) with a more stable humidity generator led to 40 ppb + 0.3 % of reading precision.
- [5] The uncertainty was determined through laboratory and in-flight measurements in comparison with other instruments using their factory determined accuracy values.
- [6] The 0.3 ppmV lower detection limit was determined at 200 mbar pressure through measurements performed with the FISH calibration stand and through measurements performed with a generally the same instrument during a non-DENCHAR measurement campaign (AquaVIT2-a). The upper detection level is limited by the condensation on the wall of the tubes and the PA cells.

It is seen that at the end of the project the instrumental achievements of all the hygrometers developed and/or tested in the laboratory are capable to measure water vapour between the ground (H₂O-VMR range of 10,000-30,000 ppmv) up to an altitude of 12-15 km with H₂O-VMR levels of 10 ppmv. With a time resolution of at least 1-2 seconds the instruments can measure water vapour mixing ratios with an uncertainty of better than 5%. These are values obtained in the laboratory under defined and controlled conditions. Next step is to evaluate the in-flight performance of the instruments during research aircraft missions done in 2011 and 2013.

5. Performance at Ground Against MBW-DP30 Hygrometer

In August/September 2013 period the WVSS-II instruments have been compared with the DP30-frost point hygrometer of the FISH-Mobile Calibration Facility. Also once, while the DENCHAR-rack was already installed in the aircraft, the SEALDH, WaSul and WVSS-II-No1 (S/N0370) were compared to the DP30 instrument. The results are presented in Figure 5-1 Discrete water vapour mixing ratio levels between 1 ppmv and 300 ppmv at 2 or 3 discrete pressure levels between 200 hPa and 400 hPa were adjusted for at least 10 minutes for each humidity & pressure level. The occasional occurring oscillations of the DP30 are instrumental origin while the humidity has been reached already after 1-2 minutes when changing to a next humidity/pressure-level. After reaching the discrete humidity level of the DP30 and the mean of WVSS-II, SEALDH and WaSul-readings, respectively were calculated over a 10 minute period and plotted against the corresponding mean of DP30 (Figure5-2). The uncertainty bars are the instrumental uncertainty of DP30 (4%) and WVSS-II, SEALDH or WaSul, respectively.

Figure 5-1: Laboratory comparison of DENCHAR instruments against DP30-frost point hygrometer of FISH-mobile calibration facility [At 15-08-2013, 26-08-2013, 12-09-2013: WVSS-II-No.1 (S/N0370); At 13-09-2013: WVSS-II-No.2 (S/N0381); At 26-08-2013: DENCHAR=SEALDH, WaSul & WVSS-II-No.1 (S/N0370)]

Figure 5-2: Laboratory comparison of DENCHAR instruments against DP30-frost point hygrometer of FISH-mobile calibration facility [At 15-08-2013, 26-08-2013, 12-09-2013: WVSS-II-No.1 (S/N0370); At 13-09-2013: WVSS-II-No.2 (S/N0381); At 26-08-2013: DENCHAR=SEALDH, WaSul & WVSS-II-No.1 (S/N0370)]. Included are sensitivity (slope) and bias (offset) of instruments (Y) compared to the DP30-reference instrument (X).

The WVSS-II-No1 (S/N0370) instrument has been compared to DP30 at 15 and 26 August and 12 September 2013. The S/N0370 show thereby a rather stable slope of 1.02 ± 0.01 and a slightly varying offset of +(5-11) ppmv compared to the DP30 frost point hygrometer. The second WVSS-II-No.2 (S/N0381) has been compared only at 13 September 2013. Here the S/N0381 instrument show about 8-9 % less sensitivity (slope = 0.9375) compared to the S/N0370 instrument, but an offset of only +2 ppmv.

From Figure 5-2 it is seen that the WVSS-II below 10-20 ppmv has no sensitivity anymore and reached its detection limit. These results are significant better than we have observed in the past in the laboratory in the simulation chamber. In section 6-7 this feature will be discussed in more detail when also comparing with in-flight comparisons.

Further from Figure 5-2 lowest left diagram displaying SEALDH versus DP30 it shows a slope of 1.009 and a small offset of less than 2ppmv. WaSul versus DP30 (lowest right diagram) show a slope of 0.982 and an offset of 2.2 ppmv. Both are in very good agreement with the DP30 and show both instruments are fulfilling the specifications they claiming in Table 4-1 with regard to precision and overall uncertainty.

6. Evaluation In-Flight Performance

6.1 Introduction

In the course of the project the DENCHAR instruments have been extensively tested through comparison with advance instruments in the laboratory (Ly(α) resonance fluorescence or DP30 frost point hygrometer) or in-flight (FISH) aboard a Learjet research aircraft during several campaigns between 2010 and 2013. All laboratory & in-flight-performance tests were done as blind intercomparisons this mean that each instrument PI has first to submit his data and then after all data were submitted at the referee, i.e. coordinator of DENCHAR, all campaign data were made available to each DENCHAR-instrument PI for further analysis of the data.

In this chapter we will evaluate the in-flight performance of the DENCHAR instruments during the in-flight comparisons made with the FISH-hygrometer, but also among the DENCHAR hygrometer themselves. The focus of the analysis of the in-flight intercomparisons of the DENCHAR instruments will be the final campaign held at August/September 2013, where all instruments (including FISH) were performing full time with total data coverage over entire campaign. The evaluated results will be discussed also in terms of the results obtained during previous campaigns.

An essential and almost inevitable aspect in doing accurate water vapour measurements do accurate temperature measurements simultaneously. To do accurate airborne temperature measurements with an accuracy of only 0.5K or better is not self evident, therefore, we start the chapter with a section addressing this issue

6.2 Uncertainty in Air Temperature Measurement

The calculation of saturation ratios and relative humidity from water vapour partial pressures critically depend on the ambient gas temperature because of the saturation pressures being steep functions of T with relative changes with temperature T of about 6%/K at 300 K and increasing to about 15%/K at 200 K. Therefore not only accurate water vapour measurements but also accurate ambient air temperature measurements are needed.

For AIRTOSS-II we compared the static air temperature (SAT) measurements made by Learjet-aircraft (=SAT_{avionic}) and by FZJ (=SAT_{ihd1}). Both measurements were made with PT100-thermistors mounted in a same type of Rosemount total air temperature (TAT) housing. Figure 6-1 show the comparison for one flight made at 04. September 2013. The comparison shows that both sensors follow each other very well and the observed temperature differences are less than 0.5-1.0 K. However, one still have to take into account that this may cause on the water vapour saturation pressure scale differences of 3-6% at 300 K and which even can increase to about 7-15%.

Looking in more detail (Figure 6-2) it showed that the SAT_{avionic} only got a poor digital temperature resolution of 0.5 K. It is obvious that a poor SAT-resolution can have a significant impact on the calculation of saturation ratios or relative humidity.

All DENCHAR instruments (SEALDH, WaSul, WVSS-II No.1, WVSS-II-No.2) and FISH are not using any SAT measurement to derive the measured VMR-data. In this report in case we calculating saturation volume mixing ratio at certain SAT we always have used SAT_{FZJ} measured by FZJ.

Figure 6-1: Comparison of the static air temperature (SAT) measurements made by Learjet-aircraft ($=SAT_{\text{avionik}}$) and by FZJ ($=SAT_{\text{ihd1}}$) during Flight madae at 04. September 2013 during AIRTOSS-II

Figure 6-2: Detail (In-Zoom) of the comparison of the static air temperature (SAT) measured by Learjet-aircraft ($=SAT_{\text{avionik}}$) and by FZJ ($=SAT_{\text{ihd1}}$) during a flight made at 04. September 2013 during AIRTOSS-II

6.3 Temporal Behaviour

To obtain a first impression of the in-flight performance during AIRTOSS the VMR-readings of the different hygrometers are displayed as a function of the flight time in UTC. This has been done for each flight and shown in Annex 2. Two characteristic flights are displayed here in Figure 6-3 and 6-4. Figure 6-3 shows the results from the first flight at 30. August 2013 at rather high humidities, while Figure 6-4 shows results from the first flight at 5. September 2013 at low humidities down to sub-ppmv levels of only a few ppmv. In both figures it is seen that all instruments are fast responding and track small scale features very well and based on time resolution of 1-2 seconds such that horizontal humidity structures of the order of 100-200m can indeed be measured. On the first glance all instruments agree rather well with each other. No real outlier(s) have been observed during AIRTOSS-II. Only below 100 ppmv then the instruments show a different behavior and each instrument shows its limitations. This behavior below 100 ppmv is rather characteristic and also seen in other flights (e.g. second flight at 5. September 2013(Figure 6-4)).

Figure 6-3: DENCHAR instruments and FISH during AIRTOSS-Flight 2013/08/30A (First flight at 30 August 2013). Pressure is static air pressure measured by aircraft. $H_2O_sat_ice_av$ and $H_2O_sat_ice_ihd$ are water vapor saturation mixing ratio over ice derived for temperature measured by aircraft and IHD (IAGOS Humidity Device) resp.

Figure 6-4: DENCHAR instruments and FISH during AIRTOSS-Flight 2013/09/05A (First flight at 05 September 2013). Pressure is static air pressure measured by aircraft. $H_2O_sat_ice_av$ and $H_2O_sat_ice_ihd$ are water vapor saturation mixing ratio over ice derived for temperature measured by aircraft and IHD (IAGOS Humidity Device) resp.

When reaching saturation or even over-saturation all instruments tend to reveal same behavior as demonstrated in Figure 6-5. Even when readings are clearly over-saturated there is no clear indication of artifacts due to evaporation of ice crystals or liquid water droplets. Although, FISH, WVSS-II-No2, and the 3 DENCHAR instruments (SEALDH, WaSul and WVSS-II-No.1) have three different inlet systems (see Figure Figure 3-1) all instruments are measuring the horizontal humidity structure in the same way. An exception has to be made when flying in warm clouds when liquid water droplets can atomize at the entrance of the forward facing inlet of the DENCHAR-Rosemount TAT housing. The last is seen for example in Figure 6-3 just after 10:00 flight time where all readings are significant over saturated with respect to liquid water. This is a disadvantage of forward facing inlet systems operated in warm clouds containing liquid droplets that they can contaminate (moistening) gaseous water vapor measurements. The results of AIRTOSS-II are very representative with one exception of the WVSS-II which same instrument show during AIRTOSS-I a detection limit of only 100 ppmv. This feature will be addressed separate in section 6.7. In Annex 2 (-A, -B and -C) for each AIRTOSS-II flight time series plots of water vapour VMR as function of flight time and relative deviations of SEALDH, WaSul and WVSS-II-No.1 from FISH are displayed.

Figure 6-5 AIRTOSS-II: Water vapor VMR of FISH, WVSS-II-No.1 & 2, and SEALDH instrument as a function of flight time (upper diagram) and the relative deviations of WVSS-II-No.1 & 2, and SEALDH with respect to FISH as function of flight time for flight made at 03 September 2013

6.4 Data preparation for intercomparison

To compare the results more in a quantitative way as a function of water vapor volume mixing ratio (VMR in ppmv) the different instruments have been compared with each other through so called whisker-scatter plots, which are in our case here a combination of:

- a) Scatter plot of instrument Y with instrument X, $Y = Y(X)$
- b) Scatter plot of the relative deviation of instrument Y to X, i.e. $(Y-X)/X$ as function of X combined with 25,50, 75 percentiles-whiskers for different humidity ranges

Doing this we have to be aware that any artifacts caused by different time response effects can slip into the analysis as can be seen in Figure 6-6. Here one can see that in the ascent and descent leg of the aircraft the relative deviations from the SEALDH, WVSS-II-No.1&2 instruments to the FISH increases rapidly. These are predominantly artifacts caused by differences in time response or improper time synchronization of the different instruments.

Therefore following procedure to prepare the flight data for comparison purposes have been followed:

- I. For AIRTOSS-II campaign for each flight all data were gridded on a one second interval. Only data are used when aircraft was flying on rather constant pressure level. This means all ascending and descending flight legs were excluded when vertical ascent or descent velocity of the Learjet aircraft was larger than 3m/s. By doing this we have excluded any artifacts (e.g. bias effects), which might be caused by different time responses of the instruments or by imperfect time synchronization of the measured data of the different instruments. The intercomparisons are presented in sections 6.5 and 6.6
- II. Further we only selected data with RHI < 90%, in order to be sure that the comparison cannot be “contaminated” by any moistening effects contributed from the inlet systems through evaporation of liquid water droplets or ice crystals when the aircraft would fly in clouds and RHI > 100%.

6.5 Intercomparison of DENCHAR Instruments Versus FISH

The comparisons of SEALDH, WaSul, WVSS-II-No.1 and WVSS-II-No.2 (Y-instruments) against FISH (X-instrument) are compiled into whisker-scatterplots as described in Section 6.4 and displayed in Figure 6-6. The whisker plots (25,50, 75 percentiles) are derived for different humidity ranges which are binned for different humidity ranges (VMR= 3-10, 10-30, 30-100, 100-300 and 300-1000 ppmv). In addition the 25, 50, and 75 percentiles of the comparison are also listed in Table 6-1.

Figure 6-6 DENCHAR/AIRTOSS-II: Comparison SEALDH, WaSul, WVSS-II-No.1 and WVSS-II-No.2 (Y-instruments) against FISH (X-instrument) respectively displayed as whisker-scatter plots (for details see section 5.3).

Figure 6-7 DENCHAR/AIRTOSS-II: Comparison different combinations of instruments and their inlet system:

- Upper left: FISH (Forward Inlet) versus WVSS-II-No.2 (Wall Plate;)
- Upper right: WVSS-II-No1 (Rosemount TAT) versus WVSS-II-No.2 (Wall Plate);
- Lower left: WVSS-II-No.2 (Wall Plate) versus WaSul (Rosemount TAT);
- Lower right: WVSS-II-No.2 (Wall Plate) versus SEALDH (Rosemount TAT)

The very first question raised here is in how far the observed features could be biased by inlet artifacts through evaporation of ice crystals? Therefore, in Figure 6-7 whisker/scatter plots for all AIRTOSS-II flights are displayed in order to compare the different combinations of instruments and their inlet systems (the inlet types are noted in the panels, see also Figure 3-1). It should be noted that obviously no deviation from the 1:1 line of the scatter plots can be attributed to a specific inlet (See also Chapter 3).

We can conclude that the H₂O range where all instruments overlap (about 100 - 500 ppmv) the agreement of the measurements is very good ($\pm 10\%$), for the range < 100 ppmv the agreement between DENCHAR and the FISH instruments becomes worse, most probably since the DENCHAR instruments are only designed to measure water vapour concentrations > 10 ppmv (SEALDH, WASUL) or even > 50-100 ppmv (WVSS-II). Between 100 - 1000 ppmv the DENCHAR instruments also agree well, but it becomes obvious that a part of the FISH measurements are too low. This is since the pressure levels where the measurements were performed were quite high during AIRTOSS II and thus for the FISH the measuring

volume in the cell became optically thick. For VMR > 1000 ppmv again the agreement of the DENCHAR instruments are in between 5-10%.

Table 6-1: DENCHAR/AIRTOSS-II: SEALDH, WaSul, WVSS-II-No.1 and WVSS-II-No.2 (Y-instruments) instruments against FISH (X-instrument) as 25, 50 and 75 percentiles.

VMR Range (ppmv)	Rel.Dev. SEALDH to FISH (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile	Rel.Dev. WASUL to FISH (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile	Rel.Dev. WVSS-II-No1 to FISH (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile	Rel.Dev. WVSS-II No.2 to FISH (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile	Rel.Dev. DENCHAR to FISH (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile
10-30	26.2 12.8 8.1	80.8 12.2 4.0	46.4 18.6 12.4	70.7 27.3 13.4	38.5 13.0 4.5
30-100	9.4 6.5 4.1	10.2 5.8 3.3	16.7 12.1 8.6	22.5 14.7 2.7	13.3 8.1 5.0
100-300	9.2 4.9 -0.5	8.1 2.1 -3.7	13.8 9.8 4.3	7.8 2.0 -3.0	11.1 5.7 -0.2
300-1000	18.7 8.4 3.7	18.9 9.0 4.4	22.4 12.1 6.9	12.4 4.3 -0.9	16.7 8.6 4.2

From Table 6-1 it is depicted:

1. SEALDH and WaSul show very similar relative deviations of about 5% compared to FISH at the middle two water vapor ranges of 30-100 and 100-300 ppmv. At the lower end (10-30 ppmv) and upper end (300-1000 ppmv) the relative deviations getting larger up to about 10-12 %.
2. WVSS-II-No.1 show similar behavior but its deviations to the FISH are about a factor 2 larger than SEALDH and WaSul against FISH do.
3. WVSS-II-No.2 agrees with FISH within 2-4 % in humidity range of 100-1000 ppmv but increasing to 12.1 % at 30-100 ppmv and 18.6 % at lower end (10-30 ppmv).
4. The differences of the three DENCHAR instruments (SEALDH, WaSul & WVSS-II-No.1) together as the arithmetic mean is listed in Table 6.1 in addition.

5. It can be concluded that the observed differences are systematical but they still range within the 1- σ confidence level of the instruments (See Table 4-1). However, the agreement is remarkable good.
6. Take into mind that FISH is calibrated up to 300 ppmv, but not above.

6.6 Intercomparison DENCHAR Instruments Among Each Other

The intercomparison of the DENCHAR instruments among each other has been done by comparison of each instrument with the arithmetic mean of the three DENCHAR instruments (SEALDH, WaSul & WVSS-II-No.1) that were at the same sampling line with the Rosemount TAT housing as inlet. All flights of AIRTOSS-II campaign were thereby lumped together. Results are shown in Figure 6-6 and summarized into Table 6-2.

Figure 6-6 DENCHAR/AIRTOSS-II: Comparison SEALDH, WaSul, WVSS-II-No.1 and WVSS-II-No.2 (Y-instruments) against DENCHAR-Mean (SEALDH, WaSul, WVSS-II-No.1) (X-instrument) respectively displayed as whisker-scatter plots (details see section 5.3). Note: All AIRTOSS-II flights were lumped together. See also corresponding Table 6-2

Table 6-2: DENCHAR instrument to DENCHAR-Mean = DM = Mean of SEALDH, WASUL, WVSS-II-No.1 as 25, 50 and 75 percentiles. Note: All AIRTOSS-II flights were lumped together.

VMR Range (ppmv)	Rel.Dev. SEALDH to DM (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile	Rel.Dev. WASUL to DM (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 percentile	Rel.Dev. WVSS-II No.1 to DM (%) 75 percentile, Median, 25 Percentile	Rel.Dev. WVSS-II No.2 to DM (%) 75 percentile Median, 25 percentile
10-30	-0.1 -16.1 -21.7	18.3 8.8 -0.6	19.6 14.3 6.0	97.3 44.4 20.8
30-100	0.0 -0.1 -2.5	1.2 -0.7 -2.6	5.1 3.1 1.8	15.7 8.0 -6.9
100-300	1.8 0.0 -2.0	0.2 -1.5 -3.5	3.9 2.8 2.0	0.2 -4.6 -8.5
300-1000	0.0 -0.1 -1.3	0.5 -0.3 -1.5	2.3 1.6 1.1	-2.8 -5.8 -7.8
1000-3000	0.0 -0.3 -1.3	1.7 0.5 -1.3	1.5 1.0 0.3	-5.6 -7.0 -8.2
3000-10000	2.0 0.4 0.0	-1.5 -2.6 -4.0	3.3 2.2 1.1	-4.8 -5.9 -7.2
10000-20000	4.4 1.4 0.0	0.0 -4.4 -6.5	7.7 6.4 2.9	1.4 -2.0 -4.6

The agreement among the four different instruments is very good and for the three DENCHAR-rack instruments (SEALDH, WaSul, and WVSS-II No.1 (S/N030)) the agreement is better than within a few percent over a very wide water vapour volume mixing ration range from 30-20,000 ppmv. A remarkable result. Below 30 ppmv the instruments deviations are increasing rapidly at lower VMR. The performance has to be interpreted individually for each instrument and here only the comparison with FISH makes sense for a quantitative qualification as done in section 6-5.

6.7 WVSS-II: No.1 (DENCHAR-inlet) versus No.2 (Wall plate inlet)

During the second AIRTOSS campaign in September we have flown two WVSS-II instruments. WVSS-II-No.1 (S/N0370) was part of the DENCHAR-rack and connected at the same inlet line as SEALDH and WaSul with the Rosemount type of inlet system mounted at the window plate of the Learjet aircraft. WVSS-II-No.2 (S/N0381) was connected to the wall plate air sampler (See Chapter 3). From the flight data shown in Figures 6-4 and 6-5 it can be seen that both instruments were performing fine until about 50 ppmv where the S/N0381 instrument reaching its detection limit while S/N0370 at about 20-30 ppmv reaches its detection limit. The results shown in the two figures are very representative for this campaign as also can be seen in the overall comparison results in the whisker/scatter plot shown in Figure 6-7

Figure 6-7 DENCHAR/AIRTOSS-II: Comparison WVSS-II-No.1 (X-instrument) against WVSS-II-No.2 (Y-instrument) displayed as whisker-scatter plot (details see section 5.3). Note: All AIRTOSS-II flights were lumped together.

From Figure 6-7 it can be depicted:

- Below 30 ppmv no reliable data, both instruments reaching detection limit (Manufacturer specification: 50 ppmv)
- Between 30 and 100 ppmv both instruments deliver reliable data
- Above 100 ppmv agreement with FISH and DP30 within 5-10% where WVSS-II-No.1 tends to measure about 5-10 % more than WVSS-II-No.1.

From these AIRTOSS-II measurements one could conclude that WVSS-II is measuring water vapor reliable above 30-40 ppmv. A conclusion that is supported by the ground based comparisons with the DP30 frost point hygrometer made just before, during and just after the AIRTOSS-II campaign (See Chapter 5). However, during AIRTOSS-I (May 2013) the performance of the WVSS-II-No.1 was not that good below 200 ppmv and it reached rapidly its detection limit of about 100 ppmv Above 200 ppmv WVSS-II-No.1 still shows reliable data (See Figure 6-8). This changing of the performance of the WVSS-II instruments have been observed more often during DENCHAR in previous campaigns. It is a typical behavior

that has been observed for both instruments (SN370 and SN381), several times in the laboratory as well as in-flight during DENCHAR.

Figure 6-8: DENCHAR instruments and FISH during AIRTOSS-I, Flight 2013/05/7B (Second flight at 7. May 2013), and Flight 2013/05/8A (First Flight at 8. May 2013. Pressure is static air pressure measured by aircraft. H2O_sat_ice_ihd are water vapor saturation mixing ratio over ice derived for temperatures measured by ihd (IAGOS Humidity Device).

During the chamber test performed in 2010 it was observed that the performance of the instrument below 200 ppmv could dramatically changing from day to day or campaign to campaign (See Figure 6-9)

Figure 6-9: WVSS-II (S/N 370) performance compared to Ly(α) fluorescence and dew/frost point hygrometer obtained from two simulations runs made at ESF/FZJ at 13 and 15 July 2010, respectively.

From these measurements it showed that at mixing ratios below 100-200 ppmv the observed deviations of the WVSS-II (S/N 370) compared to the Lyman (α) are not consistent for each simulation run. The S/N 370-instrument showed sensitivity variations of more than factor 5 at humidities below 100 ppmv. The same instrument participated in the LICC 2010 campaign at FZJ during 5 simulation runs made in ESF between 11 and 15 October 2010. Results from two simulations runs are displayed in Figure 6-10

Figure 6-10: LICC 2010: WVSS-II+X (S/N 370) performance compared Ly(α) fluorescence and dew/frost point hygrometer obtained from two simulations runs made at ESF/FZJ at 12 and 13 October 2010, respectively.

Similar to the chamber results from July 2010, at water vapor mixing ratio levels larger than 100 ppmv the WVSS-II (S/N-370) instrument show within $\pm(5-10)\%$ good agreement with the hygrometer instruments of the ESF. However, below 100 ppmv the sensitivity of the instrument declined very rapidly, even more stronger compared to the July 2010-results.

That two different WVSS-II instruments can have good and same performance even down to 40 ppmv we have observed, but also several time that the same instrument can vary its behaviour below 200 ppmv drastically. As an example the results from the DENCHAR in-flight comparison made in May 2011 (See Figure 3-2) where the SN 370 instrument was at the central DENCHAR inlet system and showed also good results down to 20-40 ppmv while the other SN381-instrument at the wall plate inlet showed that typical bad performance below 200 ppmv. At that time (end of 2011) we thought it was the wall plate inlet that would sample moist aircraft boundary layer air and thus would contaminate the measurements.

Summarizing all DENCHAR-results we conclude that the WVSS-II system can do reliable water vapour measurements above 200 ppmv, but at lower humidities the instrument can have different (good or bad) performance. It is obvious that below 200 ppmv the WVSS-II get less reliable.

7. Summary & Recommendations

Summary and Recommendations on Instruments

In the course of the DENCHAR project, compact instrument for measuring water vapour aboard research aircraft and in principle also aboard passenger aircraft were compared in laboratory tests and in-flight tests over the entire range of water vapour mixing ratios (VMR) expected for the upper troposphere and tropopause region. The major purpose of the study was to identify potential techniques for the future design of compact instruments suitable for unattended operation which agree -as far as technologically possible- with research grade high-attendance instruments for precise water vapour measurements.

In order to obtain unbiased results of the instrument intercomparisons, all laboratory and in-flight-performance tests were conducted as blind intercomparisons. Furthermore, the DENCHAR hygrometers were compared to the FISH instrument which was also operated aboard the aircraft. The FISH itself was calibrated to the reference frost point hygrometer MBW DP30 in the laboratory. The FISH instrument has participated in several international aircraft and laboratory hygrometer intercomparisons as one of the so-called 'core' instruments'. In other terms: FISH can be assumed as the transfer standard between aircraft measurements and the ground based MBW DP30 reference frostpoint hygrometer.

- All four DENCHAR-instruments show very consistent behavior in their respective measuring ranges. They deviate by less than about 5-10%, in-flight against FISH as well as among each other. They also show similar consistent results in the laboratory against DP30 (MBW-Frost point hygrometer). Thus, all results can be traced back to the DP30 reference instrument within about 10% or even better.
- Performance of the new DENCHAR instruments is generally good from VMR = 20,000 ppmv down to 20-100 ppmv, achieving agreement within 10% uncertainty or better.
- The commercial WVSS-II system can be used for VMR > 200 ppmv in unattended mode and can do reliable water vapour measurements within $\pm(5-10)\%$ uncertainty. However, at lower humidities the instrument gets not reliable anymore because it can alter its performance: Sometimes the WVSS-II can even measure very well down to 20-40 ppmv, but at other times the same instrument reaches its detection limit already at 200 ppmv water vapour mixing ratios.
- The measuring capabilities of the DENCHAR instruments SEALDH, WaSul and WVSS-II are remarkable good and are certainly comparable with the results of intercomparisons of well established airborne hygrometer done in the laboratory at Aquavit (Fahey et al., 2009).

The newly developed DENCHAR instruments have a large potential for further developments for future airborne applications:

- Instruments like SEALDH or WaSul both using laser absorption methods that are able to achieve sampling rates of 10-100 Hz may be applied for fast measurements of gaseous water vapour > 10 ppmv. This might open research areas on water vapour flux measurements or eddy correlation studies..
- The dual photoacoustic detector cell of the WaSul instrument is a very good candidate for conducting either simultaneous measurements of water vapour and total water or for comparing the performances of different inlet systems.

- The WVSS-II sensor is a good, compact and robust instrument for doing humidity measurements in the lower and middle troposphere but not suitable for upper tropospheric or lower stratospheric measurements.

Summary and Recommendations on Inlet Systems

The following inlets were extensively compared to each other during the DENCHAR project (for detail see Section 3):

- a forward facing inlet
- a backward facing inlet
- a Rosemount inlet
- a wall plate inlet

As shown in Section 3, no measurement artifacts caused by specific characteristics of an inlet could be identified. This finding is not surprising for the forward and backward inlets, since those types of inlets are well characterized and often used on research aircraft for various types of measurements, including water vapour- in the last decades. For the Rosemount inlets it was often discussed if evaporated ice residuals might influence the H₂O signal. Up to now it was unknown if wall plate inlets properly sample the gas phase. From this study we can conclude that the latter two inlet types are also suitable for representative measurements of at least H₂O.

The following recommendations can be derived from the intercomparison:

- Forward facing inlets -the only inlet type which samples gas phase + ice (=total water)- and backward facing inlet -for sampling of gas phase constituents-are recommended for use on aircraft since they are well characterized and established.
 - Backward inlets needs a pump inside of the aircraft to produce the flow through the instrument. The pump needs space in the aircraft and also have to be certified before use.
 - Forward inlets can be operated by using a pump to produce a defined flow through the instrument, or they can be operated as open system driven by the pressure difference between inlet and outlet. In this case, no additional effort for a pump is necessary, but the flow is not constant since it is regulated by the altitude dependent pressure difference.
 - The certification procedure before use might be time and cost-intensive, since they protrude from the outer shell of the aircraft.
- Rosemount and wall plate inlets are also recommended for use on aircraft. They are in use on research as well as on commercial aircraft and from this study it can be shown that both do not cause sampling biases.
 - Rosemount and wall plate inlets are both open systems which do not need a pump in addition.
 - The certification procedure before use is simpler than for forward and backward inlets, especially for the wall plate inlets, since they cling to the aircraft skin.

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- In case no defined flow through the instrument is needed and only the gas phase should be measured, these inlet types are preferable to the forward/backward inlets.

These recommendations are valid in the temperature and pressure range studied here, that is $T < 240$ K (cirrus cloud range) and $p < 500$ hPa (altitudes > 5 km). For warmer conditions at lower altitudes (mixed phase and warm cloud range) with much higher H₂O concentrations, the possibility of condensation of water in the inlet lines or, inside of clouds, splashing of drops at the inlet tip is much larger. These effects can cause inlet induced measurement artifacts. It is a future task to study inlet characteristics under conditions typical for the lower troposphere.

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9. Appendix

Annex 1: Fact Sheets DENCHAR Instruments

Annex 2: Survey of In-Flight Campaign Plots of DENCHAR & FISH

- a.) Time series for each flight of AIRTOSS-I (05-08 May 2013)
- b.) Time series for each flight of AIRTOSS-II (29. August - 5. September 2013)
- c.) Time series for each flight with relative deviations to FISH of AIRTOSS-II

Annex 1: Fact Sheets DENCHAR Instruments

Annex 1-A:

Fact Sheet for DENCHAR Reference Instrument: FISH

No.	Item	Specifications	Comments
1	Version Number	n/a,	Self-build instrument
2	Instrument Name	FISH	Fast In-situ Stratospheric Hygrometer
3	Technique	Lyman- α photofragment fluorescence hygrometer, self-build at Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Germany	
4	Platform	Geophysica M55 (research aircraft), DLR Falcon 20-E5, Learjet 36A, NASA WB-57, DLR HALO Gulfstream G500	
5	Physical size (LxWxH) in cm	48 x 57 x 45	
6	Weight in kg	45	
7A	Detection Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	H ₂ O -Volume Mixing Ratio in ppmv	
7B	Measuring Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.) of	H ₂ O VMR (ppmv), depending on inlet system either total water (gas phase + ice particles) or gas phase water vapor	
8	Response time at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	1s data at all altitudes (1 Hz)	
9	Vertical Range	5 - 21 km (500 – 50 hPa)	
10	Reproducibility/Precision	1.0 %	
11	Overall Uncertainty at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	7% + 0.3 ppmv for all altitudes but in the range of 1-1000 ppmv	
12	Daytime/Nighttime	day and night	
13	Calibration Frequency Needed	For quality reasons, if possible before and after each flight. Or alternative after 15-20 hours of measurement time.	
14	Observing Wavelengths	Lyman- α light @ 121 nm Fluorescence light @ 308 nm	

15	A Priori/spectroscopic Parameters/Vapor Pressure Equations/Auxiliary Data Used	n/a	
16	Transportability/Suitability for Campaign	Instrument and also calibration bench are transportable.	
17	Corrections needed?	Enhancement correction for total water measurements due to oversampling of ice particles.	
18	Referencing (technique, history, traceability, retrieval, validation)	FISH water vapor data are traceable to the MBW DP30 frost point measurements. This DP30 has to be routinely calibrated against others and the secondary standards.	
19	Interferences/Contamination	n/a	
20	System Availability Since	Mai 1996 at STREAM campaign	
21	Data Delivery Time	1-3 weeks after flight	
22	Caveats/Bottlenecks/ Limitations	Limited measurement range of 1 – 1000 ppmv due to optical saturation effects at higher humidities.	
23	Instrument PI	Martina Krämer	
24	Contact	m.kraemer@fz-juelich.de	

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Annex 1-BI:

Fact Sheet for DENCHAR Hygrometer Instrument: SEALDH-I

No.	Item	Specifications	Comments
1	Version Number	SEALDH-I	
2	Instrument Name	Selective Extractive Airborne Diode Laser Hygrometer	
3	Technique	Calibration free, tuneable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (cal-free TDLAS) (own development, developed in several project the last years)	
4	Platform	LEARJET 35A	
5	Natural Measuring Units	absolute calibration (ppmv)	
6	Response time at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	optical 120 Hz max, flow limited, 100% exchange time in cell is about 0.7sec at 5 l/min at 5stl/min and 200hPa	
7	Vertical Range	no limitations	
8	Reproducibility	< 2 %	
	Precision	39 ppbv at 1sec	
9	Overall Uncertainty at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	4.3% +- 25 ppmv full range between 30 and 30000 ppmv Calculated uncertainty, not measured Instrument without inlet and sampling issues, which are quite important for all H2O instruments.	
10	Observation Geometry	n/a	
11	Daytime/Nighttime	day and night	
12	Calibration Frequency Needed	NO CALIBRATION AT ALL	
13	Observing Wavelength	1370 nm	
14	A Priori/spectroscopic Parameters/Vapor Pressure Equations/Auxiliary Data Used	Databases such as HITRAN and own measurements. Complex, integrated evaluation procedure, see references	

15	Transportability/Suitability for Campaign	Transportable, 19" rack, 4He build for transportable operations	
16	Corrections needed?	after evaluation, final data are available	
17	Referencing (technique, history, traceability, retrieval, validation)	(Ebert & Wolfrum, 2000) (Schulz, Dreizler, Ebert, & Wolfrum, 2007) (Buchholz, Kühnreich, Smit, & Ebert, 2013)	
18	Interferences/Contamination	n/a	
19	System Availability Since	Mai 2011	
20	Data Delivery Time	1-3 weeks after flight	
21	Caveats/Bottlenecks/Limitations	no limitations	
22	Instrument PI	Prof. Dr. Volker Ebert	
23	Contact	Volker.ebert@ptb.de	

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Annex 1-BII:

Fact Sheet for DENCHAR Hygrometer Instrument: SEALDH-II

No.	Item	Specifications	Comments
1	Version Number	SEALDH-II	
2	Instrument Name	Selective Extractive Airborne Diode Laser Hygrometer	
3	Technique	Calibration free, tuneable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (cal-free TDLAS) (own development, developed in several project the last years)	
4	Platform	LEARJET 35A	
5	Natural Measuring Units	absolute calibration (ppmv)	
6	Response time at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	optical 140 Hz max, flow limited, 100% exchange time in cell is about 0.5sec at 7 l/min at 5stl/min and 200hPa	
7	Vertical Range	no limitations	
8	Reproducibility	< 0.5 % +-1ppmv, average 0.17% validated in pressure (1000-65 hPa) and concentration range (5-25000 ppmv) at national primary standard	
	Precision	83 ppbv at 1sec	
9	Overall Uncertainty at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	4.3% +- 3 ppmv full range between 5 and 30000 ppmv Calculated uncertainty, not measured, measured deviation are smaller. Instrument without inlet and sampling issues, which are quite important for all H2O instruments.	
10	Observation Geometry	n/a	
11	Daytime/Nighttime	day and night	
12	Calibration Frequency Needed	NO CALIBRATION AT ALL	
13	Observing Wavelength	1370 nm	

14	A Priori/spectroscopic Parameters/Vapor Pressure Equations/Auxiliary Data Used	Databases such as HITRAN and own measurements. Complex, integrated evaluation procedure, see references	
15	Transportability/Suitability for Campaign	Transportable, 19" rack, 4He build for transportable operations	
16	Corrections needed?	after evaluation, final data are available	
17	Referencing (technique, history, traceability, retrieval, validation)	(Ebert & Wolfrum, 2000) (Schulz, Dreizler, Ebert, & Wolfrum, 2007) (Buchholz, Kühnreich, Smit, & Ebert, 2013)	
18	Interferences/Contamination	n/a	
19	System Availability Since	Mai 2012	
20	Data Delivery Time	1-3 weeks after flight	
21	Caveats/Bottlenecks/Limitations	no limitations	
22	Instrument PI	Prof. Dr. Volker Ebert	
23	Contact	Volker.ebert@ptb.de	

References

Buchholz, B., Kühnreich, B., Smit, H. G. J., & Ebert, V. (2013). Validation of an extractive, airborne, compact TDL spectrometer for atmospheric humidity sensing by blind intercomparison. *Applied Physics B*, *110*(2), 249–262. doi:10.1007/s00340-012-5143-1

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Schulz, C., Dreizler, A., Ebert, V., & Wolfrum, J. (2007). Combustion Diagnostics. In C. Tropea, A. L. Yarin, & J. F. Foss (Eds.), *Handbook of Experimental Fluid Mechanics* (pp. 1241–1316). Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

Annex 1-C:

Fact Sheet for DENCHAR Hygrometer Instrument: WaSul-Hygro

No.	Item	Specifications	Comments
1	Version Number	Version #2	
2	Instrument Name	WaSul	Developed at the University of Szeged, Department of Optics and Quantum Electronics. Commercially available at Hilase Ltd as Hilase-Hygro 2
3	Technique (Principle of Measurement)	Wavelength Modulation based Tunable Diode Laser Photoacoustic Spectroscopy	The instrument is designed for dual channel operation. This gives the possibility for simultaneous measurements of water vapor and total water in case of using proper gas inlet sampler systems.
4	Airborne Platform	Subsonic Aircraft	
5	Physical size (LxWxH) in cm	49x49x13	
6	Weight in kg	15	
7A	Detection Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	Molecular Density	
7A	Measuring Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	Volume Mixing Ratio in ppmv	Standard output signal in volume mixing ratio that is based on calibrations that uses internal pressure transducer
8	Response time at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	2 sec. at Z=0-12 km	
9	Vertical Range	0-20 km	
10	Reproducibility/Precision	VMR 0.5-25000 ppmv: 0.5% of reading or 0.5 ppmv whichever dominates	
11	Overall Uncertainty at	VMR = 100-20,000 ppmv: 4%	

	different altitudes or water vapor mixing ratio levels	VMR = 10-100 ppmv: 5-7% VMR < 50 ppmv: <1 ppmv	
12	Daytime/Nighttime	day and night	
13	Calibration Frequency Needed	6 months to validate the calibration constants of the instrument	Based on experience of other similar photoacoustic spectroscopy based systems developed at the University of Szeged.
14	Detection Wavelength	1393 nm	
15	A Priori/spectroscopic Parameters/Vapor Pressure Equations/Auxiliary Data Used	Water vapor saturation pressure equations with respect to liquid water and ice	data are indirectly used in the system calibration Goff, 1965
16	Transportability/Suitability for Campaign	Transportable	
17	Corrections needed?	No	
18	Referencing (technique, history, traceability, retrieval, validation)	Instrument is calibrated by developer (University of Szeged) with a NIST traceable frostpoint hygrometer validated humidity generator.	Murphy and Koop, 2005
19	Interferences/Contamination	Not known/ up to now not discovered	
20	System Availability Since	2004	
21	Data Delivery Time	Can be real-time if necessary	
22	Caveats/Bottlenecks/Limitations		
23	Instrument PI	Zoltan Bozoki	
24	Contact	zbozoki@phyx.u-szeged.hu	

References

D. M. Murphy and T. Koop: Review of the vapour pressures of ice and supercooled water for atmospheric applications, Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc. (2005), 131, pp. 1539–1565

Goff, J. A.: Saturation pressure of water on the new Kelvin scale. In Humidity and moisture: Measurement and control in science and industry. Volume 3. Ed. A. Wexler. Reinhold Publishing, New York, USA

Annex 1-D:

Fact Sheet for DENCHAR Hygrometer Instrument: WVSS-II (No.1&No.2)

No.	Item	Specifications	Comments
1	Version Number	Version #2 (upgrade of April 2010)	
2	Instrument Name	WVSS-II	WVSS-II (Water Vapor Sampling System Mark II) Manufacturer= Spectra Sensors Inc., USA
3	Technique (Principle of Measurement)	Tunable Diode Laser Absorption Spectroscopy (TDLAS) using 2f detection techniques	
4	Airborne Platform	Subsonic Aircraft	
5	Physical size (LxWxH) in cm	25x14x9	
6	Weight in kg	3,5	
7A	Detection Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	Molecular Density	
7A	Measuring Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	Volume Mixing Ratio in ppmv	Standard output signal in volume mixing ratio that is based on calibrations that uses internal pressure transducer
8	Response time at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	2 sec. at Z=0-3 km 3 sec. at Z=3-6 km 4 sec. at Z=6-12 km	Response time slightly increasing with decreasing pressure
9	Vertical Range	0-12 km	
10	Reproducibility/Precision	VMR > 50 ppmv: 3% of readings VMR < 50 ppmv: Instable, Detection Limit	
11	Overall Uncertainty at different altitudes or water vapor mixing ratio levels	VMR = 200-20,000 ppmv: 5% VMR = 100-200 ppmv: 5-10% VMR = 50-100 ppmv: 10-20% VMR < 50 ppmv: Instable	Below 100-200 ppmv the inlet system can be the major contamination source limiting performance. Occasionally below 100 ppmv the

		Z=6-9 km:	instrument get
12	Daytime/Nighttime	day and night	
13	Calibration Frequency Needed	after 1000 flight hours	
14	Detection Wavelength	1360 nm	
15	A Priori/spectroscopic Parameters/Vapor Pressure Equations/Auxiliary Data Used	Water vapor absorption cross section at 1360 nm	Data are indirectly used in the system calibration
16	Transportability/Suitability for Campaign	Transportable	
17	Corrections needed?	TDLAS-2f detection requires regular calibrations	
18	Referencing (technique, history, traceability, retrieval, validation)	Instrument is calibrated by manufacturer (Spectra Sensors Inc) with a NIST traceable frostpoint hygrometer.	at different pressure and temperatures according May et al, 1999
19	Interferences/Contamination	When using wall plate inlet system	Wall plate inlet system can also sample boundary layer air at aircraft skin
20	System Availability Since	May 2011	
21	Data Delivery Time	1-3 weeks after flight	
22	Caveats/Bottlenecks/Limitations	Below 50 ppmv occasionally instable measurement	Instabilities due to lost of lost of detection signal
23	Instrument PI	Herman G.J. Smit	
24	Contact	h.smit@fz-juelich.de	

References

Helms, D., A. Hoff, H.G.J. Smit, S. Taylor, S. Carlberg, M. Berechree, Advancements in the AMDAR Humidity Sensing, Proceedings of TECO-2010 - WMO Technical Conference on Meteorological and Environmental Instruments and Methods of Observation, IOM-104 WMO-TD No.1546, Helsinki, Finland, 30 August - 1 September 2010

May, R., Open-path, near-infrared tunable diode laser spectrometer for atmospheric measurements of H₂O, J. Geophys. Res., 103, 19,161-19,172, 1998

Annex 1-E:

Fact Sheet for DENCHAR Hygrometer Instrument: SAW

No.	Item	Specifications	Comments
1	Version Number	Version #2 (upgrade of April 2011)	
2	Instrument Name	SAW (Surface Acoustic Wave) hygrometer.	University of Cambridge SAW DENCHAR instrument variant. Manufacturer = University of Cambridge
3	Technique (Principle of Measurement)	Surface acoustic wave modulation & detection within a crystal substrate.	
4	Airborne Platform	Subsonic Aircraft	
5	Physical size (LxWxH) in cm	15x12x12	
6	Weight in kg	<4kg	Expected.
7A	Detection Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	Dew/frost point temperature in Kelvin	
7A	Measuring Units (vmr, RH, N, pressure, etc.)	Dew/frost point temperature in Kelvin.	The standard output is a dew or frost point temperature which is then converted.
8	Response time at different altitudes (Z=0-3,3-6, 6-9, 9-12 km)	Estimated to be 5-10 s	Response time dependence is strongly dependent on controlling the dew/frostpoint of the surface of the SAW detector
9	Vertical Range in km	0-10 km	Possible to extend operation into the upper troposphere with improved heat removal
10	Reproducibility/Precision	Frostpoint temperature: 215 K - 275 K: $\pm 1-4\%$ 200 K - 215 K: $\sim \pm 1-5\%$	Based on laboratory tests in the Environmental Simulation Facility (ESF) at Forschungszentrum Juelich (FZJ)
11	Overall Uncertainty at different altitudes or water vapor mixing ratio levels	n/a	uncertainty at different altitudes/water vapor mixing levels are not possible to state

12	Daytime/Nighttime	day and night	
13	Calibration Frequency	Regular calibration of temperature sensor measuring dew/frost point temperature.	The detection is a fundamental measurement of dew/frost point temperature
14	Detection Wavelength	n/a. The measurement frequency: 416.5 - 418.5 MHz	
15	A Priori/spectroscopic Parameters/Vapor Pressure Equations/Auxiliary Data Used	n/a	n/a
16	Transportability/Suitability for Campaign	Transportable	
17	Corrections needed?	n/a	n/a
18	Referencing (technique, history, traceability, retrieval, validation)	Instrument was operationally calibrated by operation against standard calibration instruments in the FZJ environmental simulation chamber	This is not a true calibration rather a operational testing procedure/methodology
19	Interferences/Contamination	If not sufficiently isolated from the aircraft cabin air temperature	
20	System Availability Since	May 2011	This instrument version has been available since May 2011. Is a research instrument
21	Data Delivery Time	3-5 weeks after campaign	This is based on research campaign timescales
22	Caveats/Bottlenecks/Limitations	At very low pressures or when the cabin temperature is very high	System inability due to insufficient heat loss
23	Instrument PI	Rod. L. Jones/M. I. Mead	
24	Contact	rlj1001@cam.ac.uk mim25@cam.ac.uk	

References

Hansford, G.M., R.A. Freshwater, L. Eden, K.F.V. Turnbull, D.E. Hadaway, V.P. Ostanin, and R.L. Jones, Lightweight dew-/frost-point hygrometer based on a surface-acoustic-wave sensor for balloon-borne atmospheric water vapor profile sounding. Rev. Sci. Instrum. 77, 014502; doi:10.1063/1.2140275, 2006

Annex-2:
AIRTOSS: Survey of In-Flight Campaign
Plots

Annex-2A

Time series for each flight of AIRTOSS-I (05-08 May 2013)

AIRTOSS Flight: 2013/05/07A

AIRTOSS Flight: 2013/05/07B

Annex-2B

Time series for each flight of AIRTOSS-II (29. August - 5. September 2013)

Annex-2C

Time series (incl. Relative Deviations)
of
FISH, SEALDH & WVSS-II No1 & 2
for each flight of AIRTOSS-II
(29. August-5.September 2013)

